

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MULTINUTRITIONAL LOLLIPOP

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ABSTRACT

Candy or Lollipop is the most acceptable, attractive and widely usable product for children. Now a day's small children not eat vegetables regularly due to fast food. So intake of nutrients reduced in daily routine children are attracted towards candy, chocolates and dairy product the heavy sugar content products like Cadbury and other pack foods damage the teeth of children. To compensate this problem there is need of something new formulation discovered which is easy to use and convenient for the children. A new multinutritional lollipop to be formulated and evaluated. The research project is to boost immune system and enhance energy level to fill nutritional gaps which are essential vitamins and minerals. Because they do not absorb in enough quantity through regular meal. the lollipop is kind of sugar confection that is typically composed of hard candy that is arranged on a stick for sucking or licking. The benefit of current research include A lollipop format makes

nutrients intake easy, enjoyable, and appealing to children. Traditional tablet and syrup may be unappealing to children whereas, a lollipop provides a fun way to consume essential nutrient. Lollipop are multinutritional form with flavour that are meant to be sucked and kept in mouth. This specially formulated candy contains key micronutrients essential for children health.

- **Calcium:** for strong bones and teeth.
- **Iron:** to support healthy blood and prevent anaemia

- **Vitamin A:** essential for vision, and immune health
- **Vitamin C:** a powerful antioxidant that boost immunity and enhances iron absorption.
- **Dietary fiber:** To promote digestive health and regular bowel movement.

KEYWORDS: Multinutritional, Vitamins, Lollipop.

INTRODUCTION

Fig. 1: Multinutritional lollipop.

Malnutrition in India is a serious and pervasive problem despite that nations recent decades of economic growth. It commonly affects all child groups present in the community. But infants and young children are mostly affected. Because of their high demand towards nutritional requirement for their proper growth and development. Malnutrition in India stems from various factors including socioeconomic inequality, lack of knowledge and resources are one of the leading factor causing undernourishment to persist in middle and high economic group. With one of the highest rate of food disparity in world nearly half of India's children are considered underweight or malnourished by international standard. This issue is both urgent and widespread. Significant impacting India's people and it is future limiting the physical cognitive and economic potential of next generation according to the 2023 Global Hunger Index India ranks 111th out of 123 countries with a score of 285 indicating a "serious" level of hunger. Although this is slight improvement from its 2015 score 29.2, the progress has been slow compared to countries with similar economic growth rate India also has the highest child wasting rate in the world at 18.7% and 35.5% of children under 5 years are medically listed as having their growth stunted a condition that leads to the long term developed complications.^[1] Childhood malnutrition in India is a direct result both poverty and systemic inequalities according to the world bank over 389 million people in south Asia live in poverty

with India accounting for nearly 40% of global rate of the \$3.65 per day poverty line this economic hardship is a root cause of malnutrition leaving with weak immune system. Higher risk of disease and impairing cognitive development. According to data from the population reference bureau. Malnutrition is one of the leading cause of preventable child mortality in India. It contributes to serves Health condition. Including underdevelopment wasting weakened immune system making children's more susceptible to infection and disease in fact malnutrition is associated with nearly half of all child death in India. According to the world bank 22% of India's disease burden is attributed to malnutrition and conditions like iron deficiency, anaemia, vitamin deficiency, mineral deficiency widespread among preschool aged children. Malnutrition also slow economic growth and perpetuate Poverty mortality and morbidity associated with malnutrition represent a loss of human capital and productivity for the economic at microeconomics level. It is calculated that 1% loss in. As a result of childhood stunting equal to a 0.4% loss in productivity of the individual.^[2] Other indirect losses for the country's economy are caused by poor cognitive function and reduce school attachment that originate in early childhood Undernutrition in fact the education gap and consequent lower skill level of workforce susceptibility delays the development of countries affected by malnutrition. Nutrition guidelines emphasize the importance of consuming balanced diet that including a variety of foods from all major food groups. Whole grains, fruits, vegetable lean protein recommended daily intake should comprise 45-65% carbohydrate, 10-30% protein, 20-35% fat with limited intake of added sugar proper hydration and sufficient intake of essential micronutrient such as iron, calcium, vitamin A, vitamin C, etc. particularly for vulnerable population like children, pregnant women, and elderly. These guidelines based on recommendation from the WHO, USFDA and UNICEF aim to support overall health prevent malnutrition reduce the risk of diseases. Due to poor economic condition the intake of diet is not appropriate up to the value so that less nutrition are consumed. But the children are only like to eat candy / lollipop chocolate and dairy products. Due to that reason we find out something new which fulfil the nutrition that is " Formulation and evaluation of multinutritional lollipop". Which is easily acceptable by children.^[3] The multinutritional lollipop is an innovative child friendly function. So we though the nutrition fulfils through multinutritional lollipop these products aim to address common nutritional deficiencies like iron deficiency, vitamin A and C deficiency, fibres, calcium deficiency all of which play crucial role for development of growing children. By incorporating these nutrients into lollipop dosage form the product to ensure improved acceptability and compliance particularly children who may be reluctant to consumption of

traditional supplement or nutrient. Dense food the formulation utilizes natural fruits extract plant based fibres, iron, and other micronutrient all while maintaining a pleasant taste and visually appealing appearance The functional confectionery offers a promising approach to supporting a public health specially children initiatives targeting micronutrient malnutrition specially in developing country. ^[4] In our formulation the nutrients content which is most requirement of children's the candy content.

- 1) Calcium
- 2) Iron
- 3) Dietary Fibres
- 4) Vitamin A
- 5) Vitamin C

For the better acceptance of lollypop, we develop formulation using sugar, or sucrose syrup which use base material the main purpose of formulation of multinutritional a lollypop to improve the multinutritional, Reduces the deficiencies of children with regulatory taking or eating of these lollypop and it is easily acceptable as normal candy which having low cost. Some other ingredient is used in formulation of lollypop like colour, favour citric acid sugar concept of a suitable for eating on a stick is quick and easy to eating by children it is probably that lollypop has been invested and reinvented numerous instances^[5]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material

Table 1: Ingredients used in multinutritional lollypop.

Sr. No.	Ingredient	Quantity prescribed	Category
1.	Glucose Syrup	6ml/ 8.4 gm	Thickening agent.
2.	Carrot Extract	1gm	Vitamin A, Diet fibres.
3.	Ascorbic acid	0.5gm	Immunity booster
4.	Pomegranate Juice	0.7ml/ 0.7 gm	Prevent Anaemia
5.	Drumstick leaves Extract	0.9gm	For strong bone & teeth
6.	Acacia	0.5gm	Binder
7.	Sorbitol	3.1gm	Sweetening agent
8.	Beet root juice Pineapple essence	0.7ml/0.7 gm 0.7ml/0.7 gm	Colouring agent Flavouring agent
9	Water	q.s	Vehicle

Identification & Authentication of Herbal Drug. Drumstick Leaves

Synonym: Moringa, Horseradish tree

Biological Source: Dried leaves of *Moringa Oleifera*.

Family: Moringaceae.

Chemical Constituent: Carbohydrate, vitamin, Mineral. Calcium, Magnesium, etc.

Uses: For strong bone and teeth. Rich source of nutrition. Protein supplement. Antioxidant and Anti-inflammatory. Relieve constipation & improve overall gut health.^[6]

Fig. 2: Drumstick leaves.

Carrot.

Synonym: *Daucus carota*.

Biological Source: Obtain from Root of *Daucus carota*

Family: Apiaceae

Chemical Constituent: Vitamin A & C, and Dietary fiber, It rich in Calcium and Potassium.

Uses: Raw Carrot juice is a good tonic for eyes, skin, physical and mental development. Juice of carrot & spinach after meal cures constipation.^[7]

Fig. 3: Carrot.

Extraction of Drumstick leaves

- a. Collect the fresh drumstick leaves wash it to remove dust & dry at temperature 50-60⁰C. Grind the dry leaves into powder.
- b. Weigh 10-20 gm powdered *Moringo* leaves. Place the thimble & insert into the soxhlet extractor. Fill the round bottom flask with 100-200 ml of ethanol. Connect the condenser & set up the apparatus.
- c. Heat the flask by using heating mantle. At boiling point of ethanol ~ 78⁰C. Allow the soxhlet apparatus to run for 6-8 hr. To ensure complete extraction of soluble mineral include calcium.
- d. The solvent vapourize, condense in the condenser, and drips into the thimble containing the plant powder, extracting bioactive compound.
- e. completion allow the apparatus to cool. Evaporate the solvent from the extract by gentle heating. The residue contains calcium.^[8]

Fig. 4: Soxhlet Extraction of Drumstick leaves.

Extraction of Carrot

- a. Collect the fresh Carrot & wash it to remove dust & dry the slices in oven at 45-60⁰C until they reach moisture content < 10%. Grind the dried slice into fine powder by using grinder. Sieve the powder to obtain uniform particle size (eg. 500-600 μ m).
- b. Weigh 20-25 gm of prepared carrot powder. Place the powder into thimble & insert into the soxhlet extractor. Fill the round bottom flask with 250 ml of ethanol. Connect the condenser & set up the apparatus.
- c. Heat the flask by using heating mantle. At boiling point of ethanol 55⁰C. Allow the extraction process to run for 4-20 hr. to monitor the colour of the solvent in the extractor, extraction is complete when the solvent become colourless, indicating of extraction of

include carotenoid.

- d. The solvent vapourize, condense in the condenser, and drips into the thimble containing the powder, extracting bioactive compound.
- e. After completion allow the apparatus to cool. Evaporate the solvent from the extract by gentle heating. the residue contain carotenoid.^[9]

Fig. 5: Soxhlet Extraction of Carrot.

Method

- a. **Hot Melt Method (Standard for Lollipops)**
- b. Firstly, prepare Glucose syrup preparation. To take 7.5g sucrose, 4.5 gm glucose, and 1.5 gm water.
- c. Heat the mixture gradually while stirring reaches the temperature until 145-150⁰C. (Hard crack stage) by using thermometer. Remove the heat.
- d. Add active ingredient and Additives sorbitol, pomegranate juice, carrot extract, drumstick leaves extract, colour, binder. Then cool about 110⁰C. Add heat sensitive ingredient like Vitamin A, Ascorbic acid in it.
- e. Mixed uniformly and quickly to prevent lumping.
- f. Immediately pour into the mould.
- g. Insert sticks and allow to cool at room temperature.^[10]

Fig. 6: Molds with Lollipop.

1. General Appearance

A lollipop formulation's overall look is determined by its visual identity and general elegance, which is crucial for customer acceptance and trouble-free manufacturing.^[11]

2. Stability Testing

it includes variation in temperature this test is carried out for one day at 20°C temperature then the result which is seen to be the Multinutritional lollipop are stable at 20°C with room temperature Physical Stability The stability studies of formulated formulation were carried out 25/75(°C/RH) and 2-8°C for one month. The lollipop was pack and the organoleptic properties (colour, Odour, taste, mouth feel and appearances) were evaluated for assessing the stability of the prepared formulation.^[12]

3. Hardness Testing

This test is typically used to calculate the required hardness in order to break a lollipop. It conveys the notion of the lollipop manufacturing hardness. The Monsanto Hardness Tester is a device that measures lollipop hardness; the results are given in kilograms per square centimeter.^[13]

Take a 5 lollipop and weigh individually. Then take hardness tester device with Vernier calliper. The hardness and radius of lollipop measured.

Fig. 7: Pfizer Type Hardness Tester.

Fig. 8: Monsanto Hardness Tester.

4. Weight variation

Take a 5 lollipop and weight individually. Take average weight and calculate weight variation using formula. Weight variation should be obtained.

$$\% \text{ Deviation} = \frac{\text{Individual weight} - \text{Average weight}}{\text{Average weight}} \times 100$$

5. Moisture Content

We measured the moisture content using a desiccator. The purpose of this test was to find out how many moisture content present in lollipop when it was dry. The finished lollipop concoction was weighed exactly and kept with anhydrous silica gel in a desiccator. The formulations were taken out and weighed after a 24-hour period, and the formula was used to calculate the percentage of moisture content.^[14]

$$\% \text{ Moisture} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Final weight}}$$

Fig. 9: Hot Air Oven.

Fig. 10: Desiccator.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. General appearance: (as per test perform 1)

Table 2: General appearance.

Sr. no.	Characters	Result
1	Colour	Red
2	Taste	Sweet
3	Odour	Pleasant with no burnt smell
4	Surface	Smooth

2. Moisture content determination: (As per test perform 5)

Weight of formulated Multinutritional lollipop = 15.60 gm
 Weight of empty crucible = 42.46gm
 Weight of empty crucible + formulated Lollipop = 58.06 gm
 Weight after moisture loss = 51 gm
 Final weight obtained = 0.51 gm
 Weight of one formulated Lollipop = final weight obtained
 $15.60 \text{ gm} = 0.51 \text{ gm}$
 $100 \text{ gm} = X$

$$\% \text{ Moisture content} = \frac{0.51}{15.60} \times 100$$

So, the percentage of moisture content = 3.26%

3. Weight variation test: (As per test perform 4)

Average weight of 5 formulations = $W_1 + W_2 + W_3 + W_4 + W_5$

5

Average weight calculated to be = $15.96+15.08+15.93+15.98+15.05$

5

= 15.6 gm

4. Hardness testing: (As per test perform 3) Initial reading on hardness tester = 0.5 kg/cm

After breakage of chocolate reading on tester = 3.2kg/cm

Therefore, hardness present in chocolate formulation = 3.2 kg –0.5 kg i.e = 2.7 kg/cm.

Thickness: 2.20cm

Diameter: 6.60cm Radius: 3.30cm

5. Physical stability: (As per test perform 2)

Table 3: Physical stability parameter.

Temperature	Parameter	Observation	Inference
15 ⁰ C	Color Odour Taste Appearance	Reddish brown Pleasant Sweet Sticky	Sticky nature
20 ⁰ C	Color Odour Taste Appearance	Reddish brown Pleasant Sweet Smooth	Stable
25 ⁰ C	Color Odour Taste Appearance	Reddish brown Pleasant Sweet Smooth	Stable
35 ⁰ C	Color Odour Taste Appearance	Reddish brown Pleasant Sweet Sticky	Sticky nature

CONCLUSION

The development of the multi-nutritional lollipop represents an innovative approach to addressing key nutritional deficiencies commonly observed in children. By incorporating essential nutrients such as calcium, iron, vitamin A, vitamin C, and dietary fibres, this product aims to provide a fun, palatable, and health-focused supplement suitable for daily consumption. Calcium plays a vital role in the development and maintenance of strong bones and teeth, particularly important during the growth phases of childhood. Iron contributes significantly to the formation of healthy red blood cells and helps prevent iron-deficiency anaemia, which is a prevalent concern among young children. Vitamin A is crucial for vision, immune function, and healthy skin, while vitamin C boosts immunity and enhances iron

absorption from the digestive tract. Additionally, the presence of dietary fibres promotes healthy digestion and supports regular bowel movements. The Lollipop is specially formulated to appeal to children with its sweet, enjoyable taste, making nutritional supplementation more acceptable and consistent. It offers an alternative to traditional pills or syrups, which are often rejected by children due to their taste or form. The overall lollipop successfully combines essential nutrients in a single, convenient form, supporting the physical growth, immune strength, and overall well-being of children. This product has the potential to serve as an effective, enjoyable, and accessible nutritional supplement, particularly in populations where micronutrient deficiencies are common. With proper dosage and quality control, Lollipop can contribute meaningfully to public health nutrition strategies.

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REFERENCES

1. Times of India Article: <https://outreach-international.org/blog/malnutrition-in-india/> oct., 2024.
2. Chromium. In: Dietary reference intakes for vitamin A, vitamin K, arsenic, boron, chromium, iodine, iron, manganese, molybdenum, nickel, silicon, vanadium, and chromium. Institute of medicine (US) panel on micronutrients. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US), 2001.
3. UNICEF India (2020). "The State of the World's Children: Nutrition – Every Child's Right." <https://www.unicef.org/india>
4. Allen, L., de Benoist, B., Dary, O., Hurrell, R. (2006). Guidelines on food fortification with micronutrients. World Health Organization & Food and Agriculture Organization.
5. Pothu R, Aparna A, Rao YM. Development and in-vitro evaluation of chlorhexidine and flurbiprofen hard candy lozenges. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Research., 2015; 6: 3380.
6. Biswas, K. et al. (2002). Biological activities and medicinal properties of neem (*Azadirachta indica*). Current Science, 82(11): 1336-1345.
7. Kim, M.J. et al. (2014). Nutritional and Phytochemical Properties of Carrot leaves. Food Chemistry, 151: 272- 277.
8. Kumar S., Kumar D. & Sing N.(2018). Evaluation of mineral content in Moringo Oleifera using Soxhlet extraction. International Journal of Research In Pharmaceutical Science.
9. Fajriati, I. et al. (2022). The Effect of Extraction Method on the Extract Yield in the Encapsulation of Carotenoid Pigment for Herbal Natural Pigment. Indonesian Journal of Halal Research, 4(2): 97-106.
10. Gupta, S. (2016). Formulation and Evaluation of Nutraceutical Candy. Int.J.Pharm.Sci., 8(4): 169-172.
11. Singh B, Bala R, Gill NS. Mouth dissolving tablets: an innovative deviation in drug delivery system. J Pharmaceutical Sci Res., 2019; 11: 1186–94.
12. Pundir S, Lal Verma AM. Review article on Lozenges. J der Pharm Forsch, 2014; 2: 1–10.

13. Herbert A Lieberman, Leon Lachman (1991), —Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms – Tablet Series, —Medicated Lozenges|| Marcel Dekker Inc. New York and Basel, 2nd Edition, 1: 339-467.
14. Shah S, Alweis R, Najim N, et al. Use of dark chocolate for diabetic patients: a review of the literature and current evidence. *Journal of community hospital internal medicine perspectives*, 2017; 7(4): 218–221.